

THE STATE OF THE MATERIAL AND TECHNICAL BASE OF LIBRARIES IN UZBEKISTAN DURING THE YEARS OF INDEPENDENCE

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Abstract

In this article, there are opinions about the state of the material and technical base of libraries in Uzbekistan during the years of independence, the changes in the post-reform period, the conditions created for readers and library workers in libraries.

Key words: library, reader, personnel, book, fund, culture, enlightenment, employee, material and technical, conditions.

Decision No. 9 of the Board of the Ministry of Culture of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated December 22, 1992 "On the establishment of the library fund and librarian personnel" states that there are a number of difficulties in providing services to readers in the libraries of the republic. It clearly showed that the material and technical base is not perfect, the lack of normal working conditions, and the fact that the library workers are providing services to the readers in difficult conditions. It was possible to observe a favorable situation in libraries operating in all regions of the republic. The material and technical condition of the republic's libraries could be explained as follows: the policy of the Soviet government in the country was mainly based on economic profit, and the cultural spheres were in a state of stagnation; most of the employees working in the libraries were not experts in the field and could not make suggestions and requests to the organizations responsible for improving the material and technical condition of the library.

But after the independence of Uzbekistan, first of all, the republic began to pay deep attention to the restoration and gradual development of the cultural and educational spheres. In particular, the National Library of Uzbekistan is an all-state universal information-library institution that organizes and implements information-library activities in the interest of developing national and world culture, science and education in our country. At the same time, it is possible to highlight the publications that highlight the activities of the National Library, as well as the lectures and presentations of the library specialists published in the national and foreign mass media and departmental websites. Bibliographic records of these publications are regularly updated in the electronic database. In

accordance with the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated February 20, 2002 "On improving the organization of scientific research activities", the State Library of the Republic of Uzbekistan named after Alisher Navoi and the Republican Scientific and Technical Library named after Alisher Navoi were merged. The National Library of Uzbekistan will be established. The decision of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated April 12, 2002 "On the establishment of the National Library of Uzbekistan named after Alisher Navoi" was announced and the library was given a new status. In November 2011, a building made of modern architectural achievements was commissioned for the library. After the decision of the President of March 20, 2012 No.

1729 "On measures to organize the activities of the National Library of Uzbekistan named after Alisher Navoi, information and resource center", new directions for improving the library's activities were introduced. work was carried out. The book is an integral part of the culture of humanity and society, and has been a means of educating people and their intellectual development in all periods of human development.

The book was of great importance in the development of social production, exchange and development of all formations as a method of collecting and storing knowledge related to all fields. Books and writing have always accompanied the development of human thinking. Although some forms of culture and enlightenment were based on oral communication, it was only after the appearance of writing that it reached the present day and became a reality. The book is the most reliable and the most convenient means of communication created by mankind. A perfect human upbringing, people's spirituality, culture, manners, knowledge level, occupying a unique place in society depends only on the knowledge obtained from books, because it is the most perfect tool for preserving and spreading human intelligence and knowledge. The book allows people to learn about the achievements of humanity, restores relations, harmony, and mutual kindness between peoples. It serves to promote and strengthen peace in the world. Without writings and books created by mankind, mankind would not have known its past, knowledge, wisdom and wisdom, and would not have been able to develop science.

All inventions, discoveries, and progress are due to books. "The book is the soul and heart of any knowledge, the beginning of any science," said the German writer S. Schweig. Books have been and will remain the most necessary thing for all times, the balm of souls, the treasure of knowledge, the fountain of wisdom.

Thanks to books, we can get information about the interests, aspirations, and standard of living of the people of that time by learning about the libraries of ancient times, the content of their fund, the system of catalogs and index cards, and the quality of library services. The wealth of manuscripts written on ceramic tablets in the centuries before our era opened the way to understanding the Assyrian-Babylonian culture. Like other finds, it helped to reveal the history of the ancient culture of Mesopotamia, its writing, palaces, churches and other libraries. Because of them, we know that there were ancient dynastic book funds of Central Asia, libraries of mosques and madrasas, private book collections, as a living testimony of many manuscript books in Turkish, Persian, and Arabic languages that have reached us, literary sources about historical figures we will be. At the time of the invasion of Central Asia by the Somanids, Khorezmshahs, Karakhanids and Mongols, the very rich book treasures of the Seljuk state, the library of Timur and the Timurids in Shahrissabz, Samarkand and Herat, the library of the Shaibani and Ashtarkhanids in Bukhara, the libraries of the khanates of Kokand, Khiva and Bukhara, we will know that it became famous in the Muslim world. Books, newspapers, magazines, etc., as sources of written information, are aimed at fully satisfying the needs of the development of society, spiritual, social and household needs, and have fulfilled this task throughout the entire development of mankind. While written documents expanded the possibilities of mutual exchange of ideas, libraries were considered a means of prolonging the life of written works. Libraries, like other social institutions, were created on the basis of the most necessary needs of the society and developed in different forms in different periods.

The reason for this is that with the emergence of writing that meets social demand as a means of recording and transmitting information, there was a need to create institutions that could naturally store these records. Because of this, the new building, which was considered an integral part of the society from the very beginning, which ensures the moderate existence of the society, was built on the basis of modern requirements, all the conditions for providing information-library services were created for them, the latest computer technologies, telecommunication tools, equipped with copiers and photocopiers.

The management of the library, highly qualified library staff, did everything they could to ensure the speedy and high-quality of the cultural service provided to the readers, despite the above-mentioned difficulties.

Thus, as a result of the measures taken by the library management together with the library staff, in the first half of 1993, the repair and varnishing

of the floor in the study hall was completed. was placed, work on the reorganization and placement of the fund was continued, a number of works were done on dusting and organizing UP format books, 55,000 magazines from the department of foreign literature were reviewed, 40,000 of them were prepared for deletion. The deposit fund was checked and 50,000 copies of the book were examined. In 1993, despite the low supply of books to the national fund of the library, 33,071 copies of printed publications were delivered to the library despite the fact that the paid primary book copies in Moscow were not sent, the price of publications increased, and the output of publishing houses decreased sharply. As of January 1, 1994, the library fund has organized 4,919,039 printed publications. In addition to this, the internal work of the library on providing information was continued: 270 alphabet boxes were printed with a systematic catalog and various card files, more than 212 thousand cards were placed in catalogs and card files. The importance of organized book and painting exhibitions has increased in the effective conduct of public events. At these exhibitions, more than 25,000 books from the library fund were displayed, of which more than 150 were taken from the department of rare books and more than 200 from the department of foreign literature.

The organizational-methodical, scientific research and publishing activities of the library are based on the instructions of the decision No. 9 of December 22, 1992 "On the organization of library funds and librarian personnel" of the board of the Ministry of Cultural Affairs of the Republic of Uzbekistan. focused on execution. During 1992, 10,908 copies of new literature, 1,414 copies of Uzbek language periodicals worth 127,000 soums were received for the fund of the regional library.

But the percentage of books in Uzbek is very low. We can see this from this: in 1992, 738 books in Uzbek language were planned to be published, but only 471 books were published during the year when the bibcollector ordered 738 books. From this it can be concluded that only 30% of the books planned for publication by Uzbek publishers have been completed. According to the letter of the Ministry of Cultural Affairs dated April 13, 1992 No. OI-II\53, socio-political literature was thoroughly studied, and based on that, the books whose meaning was outdated, not suitable for the present time, and which were not requested by the readers was released from the fund of the regional library. The number of these books was 43,433 copies, of which:

I. Obsolete literature - 39394 copies.

II. Unusable literature-1632 copies (torn)

III. 2330 copies were given to the book exchange department.

During the year, books were brought from other cities through inter-library subscription to fully satisfy the demand of readers for books. During the year, 150 subscribers and 171 readers used the interlibrary subscription. More than 300 books and 312 magazines were brought to them from other city and regional libraries. The purpose of the Resolution of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan on June 20, 2006 "On the organization of providing the population of the Republic with information and library", which is the basis for a fundamental change in the field of library work, is the intellectual goal of the growing young generation. It was focused on providing the population with more extensive and systematic information by building new information library institutions aimed at meeting their needs and preserving cultural and moral values.

The task of information-resource centers based on educational libraries of educational institutions is to effectively use modern information technologies in organizing regular education and independent study of students and different strata of the population, to spread national, spiritual and moral values. promoting, ensuring the enjoyment of the cultural and historical heritage of the nation, providing information and library services to the population with electronic databases created on the basis of new information technologies, Internet resources, all education and information was defined as working in cooperation with the authorities. Information-library centers established on the basis of existing scientific-universal libraries are responsible for raising the provision of information-library services to the population to a new level in terms of quality, quickly satisfying their interests in the fields of science, education, information and culture on the basis of modern information technologies, and to create their own information resources and to use world scientific and educational information resources from traditional library services, to form, store and use the fund of national and foreign printed and electronic publications, to provide information resources with the help of a collective electronic catalog creation of unifying electronic libraries and databases, coordination of activities of local information-resource centers, and organizational-methodological support were assigned.

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